

COVID-19 Immunity Certificates (Passports) as an Intergovernmental problem in Canada

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Abstract

This article explores the issue of COVID 19 Immunity Certificates, also known as immunization or vaccine passports, in Canada as an intergovernmental problem. The global pandemic has demanded a coordinated response from all levels of government in Canada to address various issues such as containing the virus spread, public health, immunization, emergency care, etc. The response to the global pandemic also witnessed partial, or even, full shutdowns of the segments of the economy to contain the virus spread, followed by nationwide immunization programs administered by different provinces or territories. The immunity of the population is detrimental for the safe re-opening of the economy, and various jurisdictions across the world are exploring the idea of immunity certificates as an enabler. This article analyzes the issue of immunity certificates within Canada as an inter-governmental problem and explores possible solutions and recommendations to address it.

Keywords: Immunity Passport, COVID-19, Vaccines, Canada, Intergovernmental Relations

1 COVID 19 Immunizations in Canada from an intergovernmental lens

The COVID-19[1] immunization program in Canada is a coordinated effort between the federal, provincial, and territorial governments, indigenous peoples, experts, and partners within Canada and abroad. Canada's immunization program has been an exponent of inter-provincial collaboration with the federal government assuming the responsibility for the procurement and supply of vaccines, and the provinces carrying out the administration of the immunization programs. Canada's immunization plan [2] defines the fundamental principles for intergovernmental collaboration and emphasizes the seven cardinal elements that underpin its successful implementation. The below table indicates the division of major responsibilities between federal and provincial/territorial governments in Canada's immunization program [3].

Table 1. Division of responsibilities in Canada's Immunization Program

Federal	Provincial / Territorial (P/T)
Procure vaccinations (Canada-wide)	Immunization program - strategy, policy, and processes
Authorizations for vaccine use	P/T immunization plans
Provincial & territorial support via the National Operations Centre (NOC)	Storage, administration, and delivery of vaccines to populations
Provide scientific guidance on immunization and vaccine use	Prioritization and sequencing
Co-ordinate efforts for pan-Canadian public health surveillance and reporting	Reporting and tracking of immunizations – coverage and AEFI (adverse events following immunizations) etc.
Liaison with international partners	Coordinate and manage the administration of immunization programs
Funding through safe-restart agreement for provinces and territories, and several economic programs for individuals and businesses	P/T support programs

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Table 2. Key Challenges and issues shaping immunity certificates

Sl. No.	Key Challenges and Issues
1	Need for immunity certificates for the gradual and safe reopening of social and economic activity
2	Restoring travel across domestic (inter-provincial), indigenous, and international communities
3	Protection of privacy and security of health data of individuals
4	Evolving evidence and divided opinion among the scientific community
5	A high degree of intergovernmental collaboration and data sharing needed within the Canadian context
6	Public opinion and underlying political, legal, social, ethical, and technological challenges

In addition, all levels of governments are expected to collaborate with indigenous leaders and key partners to ensure immunization outcomes for the First Nations, Inuits and Métis.

2 The Problem Statement

Immunity certificates are viewed as a crucial enabler for the gradual, phased and safe reopening of the society and economy to pre-COVID-19 pandemic levels. While proponents argue for the benefits of immunity certificates, the scientific community is divided because of evolving evidence. There are concerns around privacy and the socio-economic implications such as stigma and its impact on marginalized communities. The immunization program in Canada being a coordinated effort between the federal, provincial, and territorial governments, there are inter-governmental parameters that need to be considered while exploring the issue of immunity certificates.

Problem Statement

“How to approach immunity certificates as an enabler for post-pandemic, safe reopening in Canada while addressing concerns of privacy, challenges around data-sharing, nuances of inter-governmental collaboration, and unintended socio-economic consequences?”

This paper also argues for adopting a human-centred design approach to defining the problem of immunity certificates. Human-centred design [3] is an approach to problem-solving that is traditionally used in design and management frameworks to bring in a human perspective to all stages of problem-solving. This paper extends this approach to intergovernmental problems. The various stakeholders involved with the problem are first explored from a human-centred design lens to frame their respective pain points and define the attributes of the problem for immunity certificates.

Some of the key challenges and issues that define the policy area are listed in the table below:

3 Use of immunity certificates

There are several uses of immunity certificates. Immunity certificates can be used to enable social activities – such as visits to long-term cares, dining out at restaurants, visits to small businesses (including, but not limited to yoga studios, gyms etc.), social gatherings such as concerts and sports events, activities within community etc. They can also be used to promote economic activities such as workplace safety, tourism, etc. Mobility, including leisure and work-related travel, both domestic and international, can be enhanced using immunity certificates. Several countries are considering the use of proof of vaccination as criteria for travel. For the successful use of immunity certificates, it requires four disparate sources of data that can be integrated to ensure that the person has developed immunity to the SARS-CoV-2 virus. These are immunization certificates (both doses), COVID-19 recovery results for acquired immunity, negative test results and negative exposure.

Figure 1. Stakeholder analysis of immunity certificates in Canada

The Federal government has already expanded the use of ArriveCAN [4] and has enforced it to capture immunization details of incoming travellers to Canada, amplifying the relevance of this data for safe travels.

4 Immunity certificates as an intergovernmental problem

Immunity certificates inherit several aspects of the federal and provincial or territorial dynamics inherent in the design of the immunization program in Canada. Implementation of the immunity certificates is thus prone to areas of intergovernmental cooperation and conflict. This paper promotes a ‘systems-thinking’ [5] approach to solve the challenges with immunity certificates as an intergovernmental problem. Systems-thinking flips the perspective of approaching the intergovernmental problem to an external one, and the components of the system, i.e., the federal, provincial, and territorial governments must be designed to work together to address the problem. It also exposes and clarifies the boundaries of the system and its components - highlighting interfaces, areas of collaboration and conflict. The below table outlines the key areas impacting the immunity certificates and their evaluation from an intergovernmental lens. Areas requiring collaboration are identified, and areas prone to conflicts are clarified with boundary conditions to make the overall system work to address the problem of implementing immunity certificates.

5 Analysis of the issue of immunity certificates

This section of the paper further analyses the problem statement from an intergovernmental lens in Canada on various dimensions such as scientific, political, social, ethical, legal, and technological. A systematic jurisdictional scan is also carried out.

Figure 2. Definition of Immunity Certificate for use

5.1 Jurisdictional scan

A thorough jurisdictional scan is done to understand how other countries and jurisdictions have approached the problem of immunity certificates. Carte Jaune [6] is a traditional immunity certificate created by the World Health Organization as an incentive to advance global immunization goals. While several jurisdictions are exploring the use of immunity certificates, the below table summarizes various jurisdictions that have adopted some form of immunity certificates as a part of their pandemic response.

It is important to note that in the United States, several states, such as Florida, Texas, Arizona etc., also have either banned or prevented the mandatory use of any form of vaccine passports. The position and situation in the United States are particularly important and have a substantial potential to influence and impact the politics and policies within the Canadian context. This is increasingly relevant as the two countries share the world’s longest, demilitarized, land border and the issue of immunity certificates is also a cross-border issue aimed at easing border restrictions. The weight that the United States bears to shape international politics cannot be overlooked. The below map details the situation within the United States as of 1st July 2021 [14].

Figure 3. Immunity certificates (passports) in the United States

5.2 Political considerations

There are multi-faceted political implications on the decision and implementation of immunity certificates. In the Canadian context, federal, provincial, and territorial politics play a key role. The current political environment in Canada with a minority federal government, and probable provincial elections in Nova Scotia and Nunavut in 2021, Ontario and Quebec in 2022 [15] can shape the issue. Political experts predict the likelihood of a federal election this fall, and the issue of a nationwide immunity certificate can likely be set aside as it has the potential to become a

Table 3. Boundary conditions, areas of collaboration and conflict

Sl. No.	Area of concern	Federal	Provincial / Territorial	Type
1	Scientific guidance on immunization (Immunity certificates)	Yes		Collaboration
2	Reopening of the economy – including trade	Yes (Inter-provincial or international trade)	Yes (P/T Economy)	Conflict / Collaboration (Boundary conditions)
3	Mobility	Yes (Inter-provincial or international trade)	Yes (Within P/T)	Conflict / Collaboration (Boundary conditions)
4	Privacy	Yes (PIPEDA)	Yes (P/T health & privacy legislations)	Collaboration
5	Immunization Program Administration and Data		Yes (Custodian of immunization data)	Conflict / Collaboration (Boundary conditions)
6	Liaison with international partners	Yes		Collaboration
7	Pan-Canadian public health surveillance and reporting	Yes	Yes (Data sharing)	Conflict / Collaboration (Boundary conditions)
8	Funding	Yes (safe-restart agreement)	Yes (P/T programs)	Conflict / Collaboration (Boundary conditions)
9	Politics	Yes - Federal politics	Yes (P/T politics)	Conflict / Collaboration (Boundary conditions)

bi-partisan issue and shape the political discourse leading up to the elections. A close look at the dynamics of immunity passports in the United States magnifies the political divide and the bi-partisan nature of this issue with arguably the red states taking a lead to prevent and ban the use of immunity certificates. A step in this direction undermines the efforts of other states implementing the immunity certificates as adoption is a key driver for the success of this program. A regulatory ban on the use and sharing of immunity data hampers the implementation of any kind of immunity certificate. The scale of the COVID-19 global pandemic also brings in the dynamics of international politics to this problem. The world health organization (WHO) has issued interim guidance against the use of immunity certificates [16] within the provisions under International Health Regulations (2005) (IHR) [17]. International politics can shape the direction of immunity certificates as the countries of G7, G20 etc. are looking towards immunity certificates as a viable option for a safe restart. The involvement of the Federal government in shaping the direction of immunity certificates is prominent as it brings about an increased bargaining power at a national level on the international stage. Public opinion is also an important factor driving the adoption and success of immunity certificates. While there are a few studies on public opinion in Canada, they have been divided and mixed [18] and are similar in other jurisdictions [19], and public opinion can change throughout

Table 4. Results of Jurisdictional Scan^{[7][8][9][10][11][12][13]}

Sl. No.	Jurisdiction	Name	Solution	Date	Type & form of Government ^[7]
1	Chile	Recovery certificate ^[8]	Certificates for COVID-19 recovery	May 2021	Presidential republic – democracy
2	China ^[9]		Partnership with AliPay & Wechat	Mar 2021	Unitary state with an authoritarian regime
3	European Union Member States	EU Digital COVID Certificate ^[10]	EU Digital COVID Certificate Regulation	Jul 2021	Various (Union of independent member states) – democracies
4	International Air Transport Association (IATA)	Travel Pass ^[11]	Digital app to authenticate vaccination status	Early 2021	NA - Civil Aviation Sector
5	Israel	Green Pass ^[12]	For access to selected services	Feb 2021	Parliamentary government - democracy
6	New York, US	Excelsior Pass ^[13]	Digital proof of COVID-19 vaccination or negative test results (opt-in) – in collaboration with IBM	May 2021	Presidential republic – democracy

the course of the implementation of immunity certificates. Public opinion will shape the politics of the region and different regions having different levels of support for vaccine uptake and immunity certificates can make the issue of immunity passports multipartite within the Canadian context. Each province or territory may choose to adopt a stance that resonates with the opinion of the local population, thereby complicating the issue of immunity passports at a national level. It can also be inferred from the below charts that the divide is not monolithic blocks as highlighted by the sector-wise support for an immunity certificate. The fact that government agencies have shown a higher degree of support for a nationwide immunization database or registry as opposed to essential businesses is an indication of how the issue is perceived by different segments of the population. It also exposes the disconnect between the choices of government agencies and the choices of the public in general.

Figure 4. Public opinion on vaccinations and vaccine passports. Source: Project - COVID-19 Vaccine Skepticism in Canada ^[18]

5.3 Other considerations

This paper also analysis other crucial dimensions about the issue of immunity certificates and their relevance from an intergovernmental lens, such as scientific, social, ethical, legal and technological dimensions. The findings are summarized in the below table:

Table 5. Analysis of immunity certificates as an intergovernmental problem^{[20][21][22][23][24][25]}

Dimension	General Perspective	Intergovernmental Lens
Scientific	Lack of consensus among the scientific community and evolving evidence on the ability of the vaccines to contain the spread	Non-uniform interpretation and tailored application of federal guidelines across provinces (E.g., Atlantic bubble vs. Prairies' response)
Social	Immunity certificates is a divisive issue at a societal level – leads to haves and have nots resulting in stigma, discrimination, and marginalization	Divides societies across Canada due to differential support, shaping public opinion ^[18] , thereby regional politics and divide (E.g., Prairies vs. Atlantic Canada)
Ethical	The term 'immunity certificates', arguably, is not inclusive by design. An opt-in approach has a direct impact on the success of the program while mandating immunity certificates can promote marginalization and division.	This paper: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. calls for the extension of similar ethics, equity, feasibility, and acceptability frameworks^[20] for addressing the ethical concerns of immunity certificates, and 2. argues for referring to the immunity certificates with the 'maple pass' pseudonym to address prima-facie concerns.
Legal	Privacy, authenticity, and legitimacy are foundational legal aspects of immunity certificates	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Health information is within P/T jurisdiction^[21] 2. P/T have privacy laws and collaborate with the office of the privacy commissioner of Canada^[22] and the joint statement by privacy commissioners amplifies privacy concerns^[23] P/T are legitimate custodians of immunization data as program administrators
Technological	Potential of digital technologies to shape the implementation of immunity certificates ^[24]	Lack of a national registry of immunization in Canada ^[25] , and P/T have disparate and non-interoperable data and technologies

6 Policy options and recommendations

Following a detailed analysis of the problem, this paper has identified three different policy options that can be considered to address the issue of immunity certificates in Canada. Since the problem is recognized as an inter-governmental problem, the responses would need alignment and agreement among federal, provincial and territorial governments.

6.1 Option 1: Non-governmental intervention (Laissez-faire) on immunity certificates

The first proposed option is a non-governmental intervention, where the issue is left to the market forces. The market forces are assumed to drive the adoption and implementation of immunity certificates on a need-basis, with regulatory oversight taken care of existing industry, healthcare data and privacy legislation. E.g., market participants, such as small businesses can ask for and gather information on immunity by check-in questionnaires etc. subject to prevailing laws and regulations. The approach also incurs the risk of overreach by market participants, such as big-tech and digital platforms providers, to gather the personal health information of consumers on the pretext of safety. This will have asymmetric impacts on vulnerable populations. A key challenge here is to align the federal government, provinces, and territories on this approach. One or more jurisdictions, provinces or territories, adopting government intervention can have a domino effect.

Table 6. Analysis of Laissez-faire approach (option 1)

Pros	Cons
No government intervention, quick to implement based on market needs	The regulatory burden on existing legislations due to new scenarios and challenges
Market innovation and new opportunities	Overreach by certain market participants, such as big-tech and digital platform providers
Enable to serve localized needs based on prevailing local market conditions	P/T with less matured markets are at a disadvantage

6.2 Option 2: Coordinated Federal, Provincial Territorial policy on immunity certificates with private-public partnership (PPP)

This option calls for a coordinated federal, provincial, and territorial policy response on immunity certificates. The federal, provincial and territorial governments can adopt a similar model to that of the immunization program in Canada. After careful consideration, this paper identifies three major pillars for successful intergovernmental collaboration and are listed in the below table.

Table 7. Delineation of inter-governmental roles

Sl. No.	Pillar	Federal	Provincial / Territorial (P/T)
1	Nationwide definition, standards and overarching policy guidance	Yes (Immunity certificate standards, privacy guidelines, data governance and standards)	
2	Funding	Yes (Support P/T based on respective needs through the umbrella of existing agreements, such as safe restart ^[2])	Yes (P/T healthcare modernization funds)
3	Administration	Yes, via PPP within the Federal domain (Nation-wide immunization, COVID 19 tests and recoveries registry)	Yes, via PPP within P/T domains (Data integration as per Nation-wide data sharing standards for immunizations, COVID-19 tests and recoveries)

The paper also sees this option as the recommended option, due to its longer-term benefits, nationwide interoperability, and the need for international cooperation on the issue of immunity certificates. Though an implementation roadmap is out of the scope of this work, this paper

makes three foundational recommendations that will guide the implementation of the immunity certificates in Canada as an intergovernmental problem:

1. Adopt key principles from Canada’s Immunization Program for Federal, Provincial and Territorial collaboration [2],
2. Define key pillars for Immunity Certificates as an intergovernmental problem, and
3. Focus on the 3 key pillars highlighted above to establish a minimum viable policy and a solution for immunity certificates.

The below table describes the pros and cons of this approach.

Table 8. Analysis of the coordinated intergovernmental approach (option 2)

Pros	Cons
Balanced approach as an intergovernmental problem with appropriate levels of PPP	Enormous effort and time-consuming to implement
Balanced regulation via protection of rights of individuals	Increased governmental involvement is not always perceived as a good
A consistent approach across the country	Complex underlying issues in terms of data and technology inter-operability

6.3 Option 3: Provincial policy on immunity certificates with private-public partnership and inter-provincial agreements

The third option calls for a provincial policy on the definition and implementation of immunity certificates with private-public partnerships for its implementation and establishment of inter-provincial agreements for meeting nationwide objectives. The federal government may choose to play the role of an observer or leave the matter to the courts in this option. This option is riskiest in terms of the fact that it enhances further divides to the already fragmented immunization program and registries. It is also prone to a high degree of inter-provincial conflicts because each province has a level of autonomy in defining the standards, guidance and policy on immunity certificates. The approach is much quicker in terms of its implementation compared to the second option as there are much lesser areas for conflict and agreement. It can also work well with certain scenarios such as to further enhance the co-operation among the Atlantic provinces. The below table describes the pros and cons of this approach.

Table 9. Analysis of an inter-provincial approach (option 3)

Pros	Cons
Balances regulatory objectives and market participation, similar to option 2 but at a provincial scale	Higher effort and time-consuming in comparison with laissez-faire
Addresses provincial and local aspirations of the society well	Inter-provincial agreements can be complicated and at times conflicting
Limited federal intervention can be perceived as good by provinces	No nation-wide definition leading to constraints in international co-operation

7 Conclusion

After a rigorous analysis of the issue of immunity certificates, this paper concludes the necessity of immunity certificates in Canada as a key enabler for the safe re-opening of the society and economy in a post COVID world. The best approach to solve the problem of immunity certificates is through a coordinated federal, provincial territorial policy on immunity certificates with private-public partnerships at both levels of government. This will enable longer-term benefits, nationwide interoperability and enhance international cooperation on the issue of immunity certificates.

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